

**THE LEVEL OF TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS OF HIGHER SECONDARY
SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the paper is to determine the extent to which the higher secondary school teachers are having the Teacher effectiveness. This paper discusses about the level of teacher effectiveness of higher secondary school teachers.

Key words: Teacher effectiveness, higher secondary school teachers

INTRODUCTION:

The teacher in the emerging Indian society has a very pivotal role to play in the social reconstruction and in the transmission of wisdom, knowledge and experience of one generation to another. Children are the potential wealth of a nation. They are always exposed to the influence of the teacher. It is, therefore, necessary to realize that emerging society can achieve all round development with the help of the teacher who acts as a powerful agency in transmitting its cherished values. A teacher is not only a custodian of national values but is also an architect par excellence of new values. But so far we have not been able to harness this extremely useful manpower. This could be possible if teacher's role is properly recognized and he is in proper frame of mind to understand the problems of the country. He should make a sincere effort to create a climate in which society can move forward.

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The mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores has been calculated to find out the level of Teacher effectiveness of higher secondary school teachers. The result of the analysis is presented in table .1.

Table.1**MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

Sl. No.	Sub-samples	Strata	Number	Mean	SD
1.	Gender	Male	512	179.29	19.248
		Female	327	182.48	21.179
2.	Locality	Rural	316	184.56	19.466
		Urban	523	179.91	20.422
3.	Marital Status	Married	449	179.75	20.877
		Unmarried	390	181.44	19.088
4	Type of family	Nuclear	755	179.99	19.740
		Joint	124	183.69	21.702
5	Educational Qualification	PG with M.Ed.,	331	181.67	20.731
		PG with B.Ed.,	508	179.79	19.615
6.	Type of management	Government	312	181.20	19.449
		Aided	192	184.67	21.251
		Private	335	176.84	19.985
7.	Subject(s) Taught	Arts	187	184.45	19.737
		Science	442	180.24	19.963
		Vocational	210	179.44	20.568
8	Age	Below 35	175	181.59	20.020
		36 to 45	525	180.37	20.367
		Above 45	139	179.83	19.076

9	Experience	Below 5 yrs	223	180.65	19.928
		5 yrs to 10 yrs	418	184.15	20.239
		Above 10yrs	198	179.10	19.905
Total Teacher effectiveness			839	180.53	20.071

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to Gender

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of male and female higher secondary school teachers. The mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of male higher secondary school teachers is found to be 179.23 and 19.24 and the female higher secondary school teachers is found to be 182.48 and 21.17. Hence, the mean values lie between 160.04 to 203.65 and it is concluded that the male and female higher secondary school teachers have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to Locality

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of rural and urban higher secondary school teachers. The mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of rural higher secondary school teachers is found to be 184.56 and 19.46 and the urban higher secondary school teachers is found to be 179.91 and 20.42. Hence, the mean values lie between 159.48 to 204.02 and it is concluded that the rural and urban higher secondary school teachers have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to marital status

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of married and unmarried higher secondary school teachers. The mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of married higher secondary school teachers is found to be 179.75 and 20.87 and the unmarried higher secondary school teachers is found to be 181.14 and 19.08. Hence, the mean values lie between 158.87 to 200.62 and it is concluded that the married and unmarried higher secondary school teachers have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to Type of family

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of Nuclear and joint family in higher secondary school teachers. The mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of nuclear family in higher secondary school teachers is found to be 179.99 and 19.74 and the joint family in higher secondary school teachers is found to be 183.69 and 21.70. Hence, the mean values lie between 160.25 to 205.39 and it is concluded that the nuclear and joint families in higher secondary school teachers have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to Educational Qualification

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of PG with M.Ed., and PG with B.Ed., in higher secondary school teachers. The mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of PG with M.Ed., in higher secondary school teachers is found to be 181.67 and 20.73 and the PG with B.Ed., in higher secondary school teachers is found to be 179.79 and 19.61. Hence, the mean values lie between 160.93 to 202.401 and it is concluded that the PG with M.Ed., and PG with B.Ed., in higher secondary school teachers have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to type of management

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of teachers working in different type of management. The mean and standard deviation of higher secondary school teachers working in government school is found to be 181.20 and 19.44, the teachers working in aided school is found to be 184.67 and 21.25 and the teachers working in private school is found to be 176.84 and 19.98. Hence, the mean values lie between 156.85 to 205.92 and it is concluded that Government, Aided and private higher secondary school teachers have the high level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to subject taught

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of teaching in different Subject taught. The mean and standard deviation of higher secondary school teachers teaching in Arts group is found to be 184.45 and 19.73, the teachers teaching in Science group is found to be 180.24 and 19.96 and the teachers teaching in Vocational group is found to

be 179.44 and 20.56. Hence, the mean values lie between 158.87 to 204.18 and it is concluded that Arts, Science and Vocational higher secondary school teachers teaching have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to Age

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of Age. The mean and standard deviation of higher secondary school teachers Age in Below 35 yrs is found to be 181.59 and 20.02, the teachers Age in 36 yrs to 45 yrs is found to be 180.37 and 20.36 and the teachers Age in Above 45 yrs is found to be 179.83 and 19.07. Hence, the mean values lie between 160.00 to 201.61 and it is concluded that Teachers age is Below 35, 36 yrs to 45 yrs and above 45 yrs have the average level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness with respect to Experience

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores of Experience. The mean and standard deviation of higher secondary school teachers Experience in below 5 yrs are found to be 180.65 and 19.92, the teachers Experience in 5 yrs to 10 yrs are found to be 184.15 and 20.23 and the teachers experience in above 10 yrs are found to be 176.10 and 19.90. Hence, the mean values lie between 159.19 to 204.38 and it is concluded that the teachers experience are below 5yrs, 5 yrs to 10 yrs and Above 10yrs have the high level of Teacher effectiveness.

Level of Teacher effectiveness of Entire Sample

The table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation for Teacher effectiveness scores higher secondary school teachers and it is found to be 180.53 and 20.07 respectively. The mean value lies in between 160.45 to 200.60. Hence, it is concluded that the Teacher effectiveness of higher secondary school teacher is average level

RESULTS:

1. The Teacher effectiveness of the teachers (entire sample) working higher secondary school is average

2. The Teacher effectiveness of higher secondary school teachers with respect to following sub-samples are found to be average:
 - The male and female higher secondary school teachers
 - The higher secondary school teachers working in rural and urban of Locality
 - The higher secondary school teacher in married and unmarried of marital status
 - The higher secondary school teachers in type of family
 - The higher secondary school teachers in Educational qualifications
 - The higher secondary school teachers teach in Arts, Science and Vocational groups
 - The higher secondary school teachers ages are Below 35yrs, 36 yrs to 45 yrs and above 45 yrs
3. The Teacher effectiveness of higher secondary school teachers with respect to following sub-samples are found to be high:
 - The higher secondary school teachers working in government, aided and private schools
 - The higher secondary school teachers experience are Below 5 yrs, 5 yrs to 10 yrs and above 10 yrs

REFERENCES:

- Henry E. Garrett, (1961).** *Statistics in Psychology and Education*. Paragon International Publishers, New Delhi.
- Adams, H.E. (1964). *Psychology of Adjustment*, N.Y. The Ronald Press Company.
- Aggarwal, Y. P., (1998). *Statistical methods; concept, application and computation*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers Pvt. Limited.
- Bachrach, A.J. (1972). *Psychological Research*. New York. Random House.
- Carter V. Good. (1945). *Dictionary of education*. New york: Mc Graw Hill Book Company, Inc.
- Good, CV., (1959). *Dictionary of Education*. New York: McGraw Hill Book Company Inc.
- Kaur & Kaur (2005). A study of teacher effectiveness in relation to teaching competency. *Recent Researches in Education and Psychology*, 10(I-II), 54-57.
- Kauts, A., & Saroj, R. (2010). Study of teacher effectiveness and occupational stress in relation to emotional intelligence among teachers at secondary stage. *Journal of History and Social Sciences*, IV(1).

- Kar, S. (2014). Teacher effectiveness of teacher-educators in relation to some variables. *PsychoLingua*, 44(1), 51-54.
- Sahni, M. (2011). Attitude toward teaching and teacher effectiveness of prospective teachers. *Indian Journal of Psychometry and Education*, 42(1), 58-61.
- Shukla, S., & Kumar, A. (2011). A study of teacher effectiveness in relation to organizational climate. *GLOBUS-Journal of Progressive Education*, 1(1), 51-55.
- Singh, J. D., & Pal, S. (2013). A study of job-satisfaction and teacher effectiveness of Primary and Upper-Primary school teachers of Bikaner Region. *Journal of Educational & Psychological Research*, 1(2), 55-58.
- Sodhi, B. (2010). *Teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers of Punjab in relation to school organizational climate* (Ph.D. thesis in Education). Punjabi University, Patiala.
- Subbarayan, P. (1985). *A study of relationship between teacher effectiveness, research and publication, and self-concept*. *Fourth Survey of Research in Education*, 1983-88, II, 1042.